

ETIOLOGICAL THEORIES OF AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDER

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Andijan branch of Kokand University Assistant of Department of Clinical Sciences Andijan, Uzbekistan Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a complex neurodevelopmental condition, the etiopathogenesis of which has been the focus of scientific research for many years. There is increasing empirical evidence that ASD is not caused by a single cause, but rather by a complex and dynamic interaction of several factors [1]. Genetic determinants: The genetic basis of ASB is one of the areas with the strongest evidence in understanding the etiopathogenesis of the disease.

Large-scale twin studies have demonstrated a high degree of heritability for ASB, with a statistically significantly higher concordance rate in monozygotic twins than in dizygotic twins. Extensive genomic studies in recent years have identified hundreds of gene loci associated with the pathogenesis of ASB. These include single nucleotide sequence polymorphisms (SNPs), copy number variations (CNVs), and other structural variants. In most cases, ASB has a polygenic etiology, with the cumulative sum of low-effect variants in many genes increasing the risk of developing the disease. In some cases, a pathogenic variant of a single gene (e.g., “SHANK3” “MECP2”) can have high penetrance and cause the manifestation of the disease phenotype. These genes encode proteins primarily involved in synaptic function, chromatin remodeling, and transcriptional regulation. However, only a subset of genetic variants explain the full development of ASD, suggesting incomplete genetic penetrance and the importance of gene-environment interactions [2]. Neurobiological mechanisms: Neuroimaging studies have identified morphological and functional abnormalities in various brain regions in individuals with ASD, particularly in the prefrontal cortex, amygdala, cerebellum, and hippocampus. For example, it has been theorized that the social-communication deficits observed in ASD may be related to dysfunction of the mirror neuron system. There are also alterations in the neural connections (connectivity) between different brain regions; hyperconnectivity has been reported in some regions and hypoconnectivity in others. There is strong evidence that disturbances in the balance of neurotransmitters such as serotonin, GABA, glutamate, and dopamine may contribute to the core symptoms of ASD [3]. In addition, neuroinflammation and immune system dysfunction are also being actively investigated as potential factors in the pathogenesis of ASD, as they may affect brain development. Theories of environmental factors: Epidemiological studies suggest that maternal infectious diseases (especially rubella), diabetes, obesity, use of certain medications (e.g. valproate), and exposure to pesticides during pregnancy may increase the risk of ASD. Prenatal and perinatal complications, including preterm birth, low birth weight, and birth hypoxia, are also important risk factors associated with the development of ASD [4]. It is important to note that environmental factors are never considered the sole cause of ASD, but may act as a catalyst for the development of the disease in genetically predisposed individuals. The claim that vaccinations cause ASD has been scientifically completely refuted, and extensive studies on this subject have consistently shown no statistically significant association between vaccinations and ASD. In summary, the etiology of ASB is a multifactorial process involving a complex and dynamic interaction of genetic, neurobiological, and environmental factors. A thorough understanding of these factors provides a basis for diagnosing ASB, developing prevention strategies, and improving effective treatments. References 1. Lord, C., Elsabbagh, M., Baird, G., & Veenstra-Vanderweele, J. (2020). Autism spectrum disorder. «The Lancet», 396(10264), 1836-1849. 2. Modabbernia, A., Velthorst, E., & Reichenberg, A. (2017). Environmental risk factors for autism: An evidence-based

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